

Separation and preconcentration of rare earth elements in geological materials using used green tea leaves and their determination by ICP-OES

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Abstract : A simple method has been developed for the separation and preconcentration of Rare Earth Elements (REE's) in different types of geological materials using the sorption property of the used green tea leaves (UGTL's). The elemental determinations have been carried out by Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometer. A number of parameters, like pH, volume, concentration of REE's, sodium fluoride, matrix element effects and amount of the UGTL have been optimised for the quantitative recovery of REE's. Separation of REEs has been achieved by stirring the sample solution (~200 ml at pH 3) with 1 g of the used green tea leaves powder and 0.12 M NaF. After keeping over night, the filtered mass was ignited in a muffle furnace at 600 °C and taken in dilute nitric acid for ICP-OES determination. The method was validated by analysing the standard reference materials SY-3 (Syenite, CCRMP) and NCSDC 86318 and the results obtained are in good agreement with the certified values. The accuracy of the method is 5% for most of the elements and the precision is characterised by 2-5% RSD.

Keywords : Separation, rare earth elements, used green tea leaves, sodium fluoride, ICP-OES.

Introduction

Rare earth element (REE's) abundance in rock samples provide geochemical informations like petrogenesis and mineralogical evolution. A large number of samples like rock, soil, borehole core, grab and stream sediments are generated during the course of geochemical investigations and their analysis is required for the REE's at trace levels, hence a suitable and sensitive technique is essential for the estimation of these elements at major and trace levels so as to provide data for the preparation of metallometric maps. The metallic, alloying and catalytic properties of REE's are also finding increasing applications in super conductors, super magnets and in space and laser technology¹⁻⁴. In recent years the determination of REE's in geological samples are being carried out by different techniques such as Neutron Activation Analysis, Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometry/Mass Spectrometry (ICP-OES/MS). ICP-OES is widely used for the analysis of REE in geological samples due to its good sensitivity, but sometimes the accurate determination is affected by the presence of major matrix elements due to spectral and non spectral interferences. Therefore the separation and preconcentration of REE's

are essential before their determination. There are a number of separation techniques available, such as precipitation, solvent extraction, thin layer chromatography, paper chromatography, column chromatography and ion chromatography⁴, besides these solid sorbents like ion exchangers, chelate resins, immobilized chelating reagents on solid support silica and different oxides like Al₂O₃, TiO₂, MgO and ZnO etc. are also employed. Activated charcoal has been reported as a good substrate for the separation and preconcentration of REE's and other elements. Biological materials of plant origin have also been proposed as sorbents like immobilized moss, sacchromyces cerevisiae immobilized on sepolite, milled peat, and *Garcinia cambogia* etc. The sorption behaviour of used green tea leaves (UGTL) are well known for the separation of trace elements like Zn, Cd, Cu and Pb as well as speciation of Cr(III) and Cr(VI)⁵⁻¹⁵.

In the present work, authors have studied the potentiality of UGTL for sorption of REE's, and a simple sensitive and innovative method has been developed for the determination of rare earth elements and yttrium which can be applied for the analysis of different geological and effluent samples.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometer (ICP-OES used was of Horiba Jobin Yvon, France, Make : Model Ultima2). The instrumental parameters and operating conditions are given in Table 1.

Table 1. ICP-OES operation parameters (Make : Horiba Jobin Yvon, France Model : Ultima2)

Parameter	Specification
Mounting	Czerny-turner
Focal length	1 m
Grating	4320 gr/mm; 2400 gr/mm
Order	1st
1st order resolution	0.005 nm
Type of generator	Solid state
Observation	Radial
Frequency of generator	40.68 MHz
Control of gas flow rate	By computer
Generator power	1 KW
Plasma flow rate	12 L/min
Sheath gas flow rate	0.2 L/min
Nebulizer	0.5 L/min
Sample uptake	1 mL/min
Type of nebuliser	Meinhard
Type of spray chamber	Cyclonic
Injector tube diameter	1.8 mm

Standard preparation :

The standard solution of REE's was prepared by dissolving Alfa Aesar (purity 99.99%) metal oxides either in hydrochloric or nitric acids, Millipore water was used throughout the study. The mixed stock (1 mg/mL) solution was suitably diluted for instrumental calibration maintaining 3% HNO₃.

Sample preparation :

1.000 g sample is taken in a platinum dish and treated with 10 ml 40% HF and conc. HNO₃ twice and treated again with 5 ml of conc. HNO₃ two times on dryness of sample mass. The residue, if any, is fused with minimum amount of Na₂O₂ and mixed with filtrate and diluted to 100 ml with water by maintaining the 3% nitric acid and transferred to a polypropylene plastic beaker for REE's separation.

Sorbent preparation :

The used green tea leaves (UGTL) were obtained by boiling green tea leaves with water for about 8 h to remove any soluble dirt and coloured components. The leaves were dried at 105 °C for 24 h and the dried tea leaves crushed and sieved to obtain a particle size in the range of 50–100 mesh.

Procedure for preconcentration/separation of REE's :

The entire sample solution was diluted to about 150 ml with water, and mixed with 10 ml of 2.4 M NaF and the acidity maintained at pH 3 by adding either dilute HNO₃ or NaOH solutions. The content was stirred for about 5 min with a teflon rod after adding 1 g of the used green tea leaves powder and kept overnight. The residue was filtered through Whatman 542 and taken in a platinum dish, and ignited in a muffle furnace at 600 °C for one hour. The content was extracted with HNO₃ by heating, maintaining 3% acidity and diluted to 25 ml. ICP-OES determination of REE's and Y was carried out after the instrument calibration.

Results and discussion

The geological materials contain high amount of iron and aluminium which interfere in complete recovery of REE's using UGTL. This may be due to adsorption of these elements on UGTL which reduce the adsorption of REE's. In order to overcome this problem, tartaric acid, citric acid and sodium fluoride were used to mask Fe and Al to get complete recovery of REE's. It was observed that addition of 10 ml of 2.4 M NaF to the sample solution maintained at pH 3 facilitated the better.

Effect of pH on the sorption of REE's :

The adsorption of REE's has been carried out, using 200 µg concentration level of each, in the presence of 10 ml of 2.4 M NaF and also in absence of NaF and the pH varied from 1 to 6, to this 1 g of used green tea leaves (UGTL) was added. The results obtained for La, Eu and Yb shows that more than 90% REE's were recovered above pH 6 in the absence of NaF, while a plateau is obtained from pH 3 onward in presence of NaF for the similar recoveries (Figs. 1 and 2). The possible reason for the retention of REE's may be due to the exchange of cationic forms of analytes with ions of the carboxylic acid functional groups or various functional groups

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on recoveries of REE's (La, Eu, Yb = 200 µg each, 1 g UGTL).

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on recoveries of REE's (La, Eu, Yb = 200 µg each, 1 g UGTL, 10 ml of 2.4 M NaF).

(sulphates, amino, phosphate and thiol moieties that are associated with cellulose, proteins and lignins) found on the surface of the cell wall in UGTL. In the presence of iron (25–200 mg), the sample solution becomes turbid due to hydrolysis beyond pH 3 even in the presence of NaF. Therefore pH 3.0 was selected as optimum for the subsequent experiments (Figs. 1 and 2).

Role of NaF and UGTL for the recovery of REE's :

A study on the role of NaF and UGTL individually as well as in combination has been carried out for the recovery of REE's at pH 3. A total of 96 microgram of REE (i.e. 6 microgram each) were treated with (i) 10 ml 2.4 M

of NaF alone, (ii) 1 g of UGTL alone and (iii) 10 ml 2.4 M NaF + 1 g UGTL and stirred for 5 min and kept it for overnight equilibrium. The study indicates that NaF alone recovered upto 60–63 %, UGTL alone recovered upto 68–72 % while a combination of both recovered upto 95 % and more elements studied (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Recovery of REE's (Eu, Tb, Ho, Tm, Yb, Lu = 200 µg each, pH 3) in presence and absence of NaF and UGTL.

Role of UGTL in the recovery of REE's :

The recovery studies of La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Dy and Er of 200 µg each with the variable amounts of UGTL (0.2–1.5 g) have been carried out at pH 3 in the presence of NaF. Recovery of the above elements shows that UGTL ranging from 0.2–1.5 g is sufficient for the recovery from 90–95 %. 1 g of UGTL was selected as optimum for the quantitative recoveries of REE's in geological samples. The recovery of La, Ce and Nd has been presented graphically in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Effect of amount of used green tea leaves on recoveries of REE's (Ce, La, Nd = 200 µg each, pH 3).

REE's recovery with contact time :

The recoveries of REE's like Eu, Tb, Ho, Tm, Yb and Lu monitored with contact time ranging from 30 min to 16 h. It was observed that there is gradual increase in retention of analytes studied. A maximum recovery of more than 95% has been achieved by keeping the sample solution in contact with UGTL for overnight (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Effect of time on recoveries of REE's (Eu, Tb, Ho = 200 µg each, pH 3, 1 g UGTL).

Effect of iron on recoveries of rare earth elements :

The influence of iron on the recovery of REE's (200 µg each) was studied using different concentrations of

iron 25 to 200 mg in the sample solutions at pH 3 and 1 g UGTL in 200 ml volume. It was observed that there is negligible loss of REE's in the presents of 100 mg of iron, and beyond 100 mg iron, there is a slight decrease in recovery (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Effect of iron on recoveries of rare earth elements at pH 3 and 1 g UGTL.

Analytical application :

The proposed method was applied for the determination of REE's in certified reference materials SY-3 (Synenite, CCRMP) and NCSDC86318 as well as some pre-analysed samples. The analytical results obtained are in good agreement with the recommended values and the recoveries were in the range of 92–99% (Tables 2 and 3).

Table 2. Recoveries of REE's in standard reference materials by the proposed separation method

Sl. No.	REE	Wavelength (nm)	SY-3			NCSDC86318		
			Reported value (µg/g)	Obtained value by proposed method (µg/g)	Recovery (%)	Reported value (µg/g)	Obtained value by proposed method (µg/g)	Recovery (%)
1.	La	333.749	1350	1305	97	1961	1925	98
2.	Ce	418.660	2200	2100	95	431	410	95
3.	Pr	422.293	120	110	92	736	705	96
4.	Nd	430.357	800	775	97	3429	3385	99
5.	Sm	442.434	100	96	96	1724	1695	98
6.	Eu	381.965	14	13	93	18.6	18	97
7.	Gd	342.246	105	101	96	2168	2115	98
8.	Tb	350.917	11	10	91	467	435	93
9.	Dy	353.170	80	75	94	3223	3188	99
10.	Ho	345.600	20	19	95	558	532	95
11.	Er	349.910	50	46	92	1749	1715	98
12.	Tm	346.221	8	7.5	94	271	255	94
13.	Yb	328.937	65	59	91	1844	1805	98
14.	Lu	261.542	8	7.5	91	263	245	93
15.	Y	371.029	740	723	98	17008	16785	99

Table 3. Analytical results of the separation of REE's by the proposed method and ICP-OES determination in natural rock samples

Sl. No.	REE	AMD-1 (K-653) Albitised Granite gneiss			AMD-2 (K-655) Albitised Granite gneiss			AMD-3 (K-660) Albitised Granite gneiss		
		Obtained value by oxalate precipitation method ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Obtained value by proposed method ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Recovery (%)	Obtained value by oxalate precipitation method ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Obtained value by proposed method ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Recovery (%)	Obtained value by oxalate precipitation method ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Obtained value by proposed method ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	Recovery (%)
		1.	La	481	455	96	272	259	95	331
2.	Ce	594	560	94	282	272	96	388	380	98
3.	Pr	47	47	100	16	15	94	29	27	93
4.	Nd	195	183	94	61	57	93	108	102	94
5.	Sm	52	50	96	19	17	90	26	24	92
6.	Eu	6	5.5	92	2	1.80	90	3	2.8	93
7.	Gd	46	43	93	22	20	91	25	23	92
8.	Tb	8	7.5	94	5	4.5	90	6	5	92
9.	Dy	60	57	95	32	30	94	23	22	96
10.	Ho	12	11	92	7	6.5	93	4	3.7	93
11.	Er	42	40	95	26	24	92	18	17	94
12.	Tm	6	5.5	92	4	3.8	95	2	1.8	90
13.	Yb	36	33	92	26	24	92	16	15	94
14.	Lu	5	4.5	90	4	3.8	95	3	2.8	93
15.	Y	266	247	93	158	147	93	107	102	95

Conclusion

The proposed method of separation and preconcentration of rare earth elements in geological materials using used green tea leaves (UGTL) at pH 3 in the presence of 0.12 M sodium fluoride and their determination by ICP-OES is alternative method for the separation of REE's from ppm to percentage level. It can be applied for quantitative recovery in different geological samples.

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